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Linguopoetic Features Of Expressing The Psychology Of Everyday Life In The Stories Of O'tkir Hoshimov

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Annotation. The article analyzes the linguopoetic features of expressing the psychology of everyday life in Utkir Hoshimov's stories. The author explores the methods of revealing the inner world of characters through internal monologue, free indirect speech, psychological description, and symbolic-metaphorical means. The specific structure of speech genres in the literary text, narrative organization, and functional features of stylistic means in conveying psychological content are identified. It is substantiated that Utkir Hoshimov's work creates a harmonious synthesis of psychologism, realism, and national identity.

Keywords: linguopoetics, psychology of everyday life, internal monologue, free indirect speech, literary discourse, psychological realism.

Introduction.

The creative heritage of Otkir Hoshimov, one of the prominent representatives of the psychological realism trend in Uzbek literature, requires in-depth research from the point of view of modern literary studies and linguopoetics. The writer's stories are devoted to expressing the everyday psychology of ordinary people, the world of deep and subtle emotions through special linguistic means. Linguopoetic analysis of a literary text makes it possible to determine the aesthetic functions of language means in a work of art, their role in revealing psychological content [1] The development of modern methodology for linguistic analysis of a literary text in contemporary linguopoetics, the results achieved in the areas of psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics and discourse analysis indicate the need to study the features of expressing the psychology of everyday life in the works of Otkir Hoshimov in a new approach. The study of linguistic manifestations of psychological content in literary and artistic speech is of particular importance as an intersecting issue of literary text linguistics, stylistics and literary studies [2]. The work of Otkir Hoshimov has been studied by many researchers from the point of view of literary criticism. Scholars such as Q. Yuldoshev, N. Shermuhamedova, B. Nazarov, H. Boltaboev analyzed the writer's artistic skill, thematic and ideological features of his works [3]. However, the linguopoetic aspects of expressing the psychology of everyday life in Otkir Hoshimov's stories have not been sufficiently studied as a special object of research. The problems of expressing psychologism in a literary text have been widely studied in world literary criticism and linguistics. Such prominent linguists as M.M. Bakhtin,

V.V. Vinogradov, G.O. Vinokur, B.A. Larin have studied the issues of linguistic formation of psychological content in literary speech. Categories such as free indirect speech, internal monologue, psychonarratology are of great importance in the linguopoetic analysis of a literary text [4].

In modern linguopoetics, modern methods such as cognitive approach, conceptual analysis, discourse strategies allow for a deeper understanding of the literary text. Language units are not only carriers of meaning, but also appear as a means of modeling a certain psychological state [5].

In the process of linguopoetic analysis, attention is paid to the following areas:

- 1) the uniqueness of speech genres and their role in expressing psychological content;
- 2) the stylistic functions of lexical-semantic and grammatical means;
- 3) the importance of tropes and figurative means in revealing psychological content;
- 4) the features of the narrative structure and the change in the point of view of storytelling.

In Otkir Hoshimov's stories, internal monologue and free indirect speech are widely used to reveal the inner world of the characters. Free indirect speech is a peculiar combination of the author's speech and the hero's inner speech, in which the hero's thoughts are conveyed in the tone of the author's speech, but directly reflect the psychological state of the hero. In the story "Between Two Doors," the main character Mahkam's emotional experiences are very impressively conveyed through free indirect speech: "Mahkam suddenly felt alone. No one understands him. Even those closest to him. Why did this happen? Who is to blame for this?" The interrogative sentences in this passage indicate that the hero is conducting an internal dialogue, talking to himself. Grammatically, this is the author's speech (third person, past tense), but semantically, it is the hero's thoughts. Internal monologue is a means of directly conveying to the reader the hero's process of thinking about his problems, feelings, doubts, and prospects in everyday life. Otkir Hoshimov skillfully uses this technique, revealing deep psychological processes hidden behind ordinary life events. In expressing the psychology of everyday life, the writer effectively uses everyday vocabulary, elements of folk oral art, and phraseological units. These tools reflect the national character traits of the characters, their social environment, and their cultural background.

In the story "The Works of the World", the dialogues of the characters use speech formulas typical of everyday speech: "Hello, brother, how are you?", "No problem, everything is fine", "That's not the point." These expressions not only create the style

of speech, but also express the relationship and psychological states of the characters. Phraseological units serve to emphasize the emotional state of the characters: expressions such as “heart ached”, “heart burned”, “heart was not satisfied”, “eyes were filled with tears” convey the psychological state in a figurative and impressive way. Otkir Hoshimov uses such means, which have acquired a national flavor, to increase the psychological depth of the literary text. The writer widely uses symbols and metaphors to reflect the psychology of everyday life. Symbolic images deepen the conceptual structure of the text, make the content multifaceted. In the story “Between Two Doors”, the title itself has a symbolic meaning: between two doors - two worlds, two life spans, the obligation to make a choice, a state of uncertainty. Metaphors make the mental state of the characters expressive and illustrative. For example, metaphorical expressions such as “His heart sank”, “His heart froze”, “His thoughts floated like clouds” transform abstract psychological states into concrete figurative images. This enhances the reader's empathetic perception. The natural landscape also acts as a means of psychological imagery. The writer shows the inner state of the characters through the external environment: a dark night is the hero's depressed mood, a bright dawn is the emergence of hope. This psychological parallelism comes from folk oral creativity and continues the national literary tradition.

The narrative structure of Otkir Hoshimov's stories also serves to express the psychology of everyday life. The writer often uses the third-person narrative method, but this narrative position allows you to delve deeper into the inner world of the hero. In the story "Lifetimes in a Dream", the boundary between events taking place in a dream and in reality disappears. This narrative method shows the complex connections between the subconscious and conscious psyche of the hero. The use of time shifts, retrospection, and introspection elements gives the story psychological depth. Focalization - a change in the narrative point of view - is also an important technique. The writer describes events from the perspectives of different characters, which emphasizes the multifaceted nature and psychological complexity of events. Each character reveals his own individual psychological world and perceives the same situation differently. In Otkir Hoshimov's stories, dialogue is not only a means of plot development, but also a means of creating a psychological portrait of the characters. In the dialogue, the speech of the characters reflects their social status, spiritual world, level of education, and national character traits. The subtle structure of the dialogue reveals hidden conflicts, misunderstandings, and emotional contradictions between the characters. Pragmatic categories such as the difference between the spoken and the unspoken meaning, implicature, and presupposition provide the psychological depth of the dialogue. Within the framework of Bakhtinian polyphony theory, the interrelation of different voices, positions, and worldviews is

observed in the works of Otkir Hoshimov. Each character has his own independent "I," and the author listens to all of them and takes their positions into account equally. This opens up wide opportunities for the psychological depiction of everyday life. The linguopoetic features of expressing the psychology of everyday life in Otkir Hoshimov's stories are associated with the uniqueness of his creative style. The writer reveals the complex inner world of a person through ordinary everyday events. In this regard, language tools perform not only a descriptive, but also an expressive-emotional function. Free indirect speech is widely used in the works of Otkir Hoshimov, creating a harmony between the inner speech of the hero and the author's speech. This method brings the reader closer to the mental state of the hero, enhances the empathetic effect. Internal monologue directly reflects the flow of thoughts of the hero and shows the dynamics of mental experiences. Lexical-semantic means, especially everyday vocabulary and phraseological units, create a national cultural context. This connects the heroes with the national character traits of the Uzbek people, places them within the framework of the national-cultural space. Symbolic and metaphorical means deepen the conceptual level of the text, create several layers of meaning. The features of the narrative structure - focalization, time change, retrospection and introspection - make the psychological portrait of the heroes multifaceted. Dialogue and polyphony reflect the clash of different minds, positions and worldviews, which shows the complexity of the psychology of everyday life.

The study of the linguopoetic features of expressing the psychology of everyday life in the stories of Otkir Hoshimov allows us to formulate the following conclusions: First, free indirect speech and internal monologue are the main linguopoetic tools of the writer, revealing the psychological experiences, thoughts and internal conflicts of the characters. Second, the lexicon of everyday speech, phraseological units and elements of folk oral creativity create a national color and place the characters in a national-cultural context. Third, symbolic and metaphorical means provide the conceptual depth of the text and make the psychological content figurative and impressive. Fourth, the features of the narrative structure - focalization, time change, retrospection - make the psychological portrait of the characters complex and multifaceted. Fifth, dialogue and polyphony show the interaction of different voices and positions, which allows for a complete and true reflection of the psychology of everyday life.

In the work of Otkir Hoshimov, a harmony of psychological realism, national characteristics and modern linguopoetic techniques is created. His stories are considered an example of a deep and complete reflection of the psychology of everyday life in Uzbek literature. In further research, it is promising to study the

means of psychological imagery in Otkir Hoshimov's novels, as well as his artistic world from the point of view of cognitive linguistics and psycholinguistics.

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